

Effectiveness Of Instrument-Assisted Soft Tissue Mobilization Technique In The Management Of Tendinopathies: A Literature Review

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Received: 21st Apr. 2026

Revised: 04th Jun. 2026

Accepted: 11th Jun. 2026

ABSTRACT

Background: Tendinopathies are common musculoskeletal conditions affecting tendons such as the Achilles, patellar, rotator cuff, and lateral elbow. They usually occur due to repetitive stress, overuse, or improper loading of the tendon and can cause pain, stiffness, and reduced functional ability. This is a technique that uses specially designed instruments to treat soft tissue restrictions and support tissue healing.

Materials and Methods: The articles used were found using databases such as Google Scholar, PubMed, PMC, and Science Direct. Studies published between 2015 and 2025 were screened using keywords including “Instrument-Assisted Soft Tissue Mobilization”, “Graston Technique”, “ASTYM therapy”, and “Tendinopathies”. Only studies assessing outcomes like pain, ROM, strength, and recovery were included.

Results: After screening the articles, four relevant studies were considered in this review. The findings showed that it can reduce pain, enhance strength, and enhance functional outcomes in patients with Tendinopathies. Studies also suggested that combining IASTM with exercise programs may lead to faster improvement compared to exercise alone.

Discussion: This literature review was conducted to summarize the beneficial effects of instrument assisted soft tissue manipulation in the management of tendinopathies. This technique has potential beneficial effects in enhancing the quality of life. Limitations of the study included limited access to the databases and robust quality analysis of the included studies.

Conclusion: IASTM appears to be a helpful addition to Tendinopathies rehabilitation, especially when combined with therapeutic exercises. However, more study with larger sample sizes and longer follow-ups is required to get its prolonged effectiveness.

Keywords: Graston Technique, IASTM, Instrument-Assisted Soft Tissue Mobilization, Tendinopathies.

INTRODUCTION

Tendinopathies are a group of conditions that affect the tendons, the strong connective tissues that attach muscles to bones and allow smooth body movement. These problems usually develop when a tendon is exposed to repeated stress, excessive loading, or poor movement technique without adequate time for recovery. Over time, this repeated strain can irritate the tendon and reduce its ability to handle normal mechanical stress. As a result,

individuals may experience symptoms such as pain, stiffness, swelling, and difficulty performing everyday activities or sports-related movements. Two commonly used terms related to these conditions are tendinitis and tendinosis. Tendinitis usually refers to an acute inflammatory response caused by sudden overload, while tendinosis describes a more chronic condition in which the tendon undergoes structural degeneration and becomes weaker and less organized [1].

Research has shown that long-standing tendinopathy is often associated with changes in the tendon structure, including breakdown of collagen fibres, irregular fibre alignment, increased formation of small blood vessels, and alterations over normal healing of the tendon. Several factors can increase the risk of developing tendinopathy, such as repetitive occupational activities, sports overuse, increasing age, metabolic conditions like diabetes, obesity, hormonal changes, and the use of certain medications. These conditions most commonly affect tendons such as the tendon of Achilles, patellar tendon, rotator cuff tendons of the shoulder, and inflammation of the lateral epicondyle. Because tendinopathies can interfere with daily activities, work performance, and athletic participation, they may significantly reduce an individual's quality of life. For this reason, proper rehabilitation is essential. Understanding the structural and functional changes occurring in the tendon helps physiotherapists design treatment programs that not only relieve pain but also restore tendon strength, improve loading capacity, and support long-term recovery [2].

IASTM is a manual therapy technique in which specially designed instruments are used to treat soft tissue restrictions. These instruments allow the therapist to detect subtle changes within the soft tissues and apply controlled pressure more precisely than manual techniques alone. When applied to an affected tendon or its surrounding structures, the instrument can help identify areas that are stiff, thickened, or restricted due to adhesions or limited tissue mobility. The principle behind IASTM is that the controlled mechanical stimulation produced by the instrument may trigger a some inflammation that increases the healing process [1].

Through this stimulation, cellular activity such as fibroblast production may increase, promoting collagen synthesis and improved tissue remodelling. In addition, IASTM may improve local blood circulation and improve the sliding of tissue layers, which can contribute to improved mobility and reduced discomfort. IASTM can influence tendon

stiffness and joint mobility, which may help the tendon respond more effectively to therapeutic exercise. In clinical practice, IASTM is often used alongside progressive loading programs because it may reduce tissue sensitivity, improve soft tissue mobility, and prepare the tendon for strengthening exercises. Although further high-quality research is still needed, the technique is increasingly being used in physiotherapy settings as a supportive intervention for patients who experience persistent pain, restricted movement, or limited improvement with exercise therapy alone [3].

Tendinopathies are widely prevalent and many individuals continue to experience symptoms even after receiving standard treatment approaches such as rest, medication, or basic physiotherapy exercises. Therefore, it is important to investigate whether additional techniques like IASTM can provide meaningful clinical benefits. The purpose of this literature review is to explore and summarize the current scientific evidence regarding the use of IASTM in treating tendon-related disorders. This review examines how IASTM is used in the treatment of various tendinopathies. It also evaluates its effects on outcomes such as pain reduction, improvement in mobility, tendon stiffness, functional performance, and tissue response. Another important aspect considered in this review is whether IASTM works more effectively as a standalone treatment or when combined with exercise-based rehabilitation programs. At the same time, this review aims to identify limitations within the current studies, with small sample sizes, short follow-up periods, and differences in treatment protocols. Recognizing these limitations can help guide future studies and improve the quality of evidence available in this field. Overall, this review seeks to provide a clear and practical understanding of the role of IASTM in the management of tendinopathies, helping physiotherapists, students, and researchers make more informed clinical decisions based on current evidence [4].

Research Gap: Evidence on IASTM in tendinopathy remains limited due to small

trials, heterogeneous protocols and short follow-ups [4].

OBJECTIVES

To summarize the effectiveness of instrument assisted soft tissue mobilization in reducing pain and improving functional outcomes like range of motion, grip strength and overall physical performance when combined with exercise-based rehabilitation programs amongst the individuals suffering from tendinopathies.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. **Cheatham et al., (2016)** conducted a review study to systematically appraise the current evidence assessing the effects of IASTM as an intervention to treat a musculoskeletal pathology or to enhance joint ROM. A search of the literature was conducted in the PubMed, PEDro, Science Direct, and the EBSCOhost databases including manual searches with keywords : instrument; assisted; augmented; soft-tissue; mobilization; Graston®; and technique. A total of 7 randomized controlled trials were appraised. Five of the studies measured an IASTM intervention versus a control or alternate intervention group for a musculoskeletal pathology. The results of the studies were insignificant ($p > .05$) with both groups displaying equal outcomes. Two studies measured an IASTM intervention versus a control or alternate intervention group on the effects of joint ROM. The IASTM intervention produced significant ($P < .05$) short term gains up to 24 hours. The literature measuring the effects of IASTM is still emerging. Their review study concluded that insignificant results which challenges the efficacy of IASTM as a treatment for common musculoskeletal pathology, which may be due to the methodological variability among studies. There appears to be some evidence supporting its ability to increase short term joint ROM [5].
2. **Wadhwa et al., (2025)** conducted a scoping literature review to find out the Impact of Instrument-Assisted Soft-Tissue Mobilization (IASTM) on the Functional

Status of Myofascial Structures. In this scoping literature review, a thorough search was performed across PubMed, Cochrane, and Google Scholar. The articles were screened according to specific inclusion criteria, ultimately identifying 14 studies: 12 randomized controlled trials and 2 quasi-experimental studies. These studies were selected for their relevance to myofascial conditions and IASTM interventions, while excluding those that were irrelevant or did not focus on IASTM. The findings reveal that both IASTM and stretching effectively improved ankle dorsiflexion ROM. However, neither intervention significantly altered pain sensitivity or muscle stiffness. **Their study concluded that IASTM was safe and effective in reducing joint stiffness, but its impact on muscle properties was limited.** The study highlights the need for further research to explore additional outcome measures, refine intervention protocols, and investigate tool designs to optimize therapeutic effectiveness. Limitations include variability in methodologies and small sample sizes, which may affect the result's consistency and generalizability [6].

3. **Singh et al., (2024)** conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis to evaluate the effectiveness of IASTM in management of athletic and musculoskeletal conditions. An investigation of the literature was carried out using the databases PubMed, PEDro, and the Cochrane Library. Eighteen studies were included for qualitative synthesis, and six were selected for further quantitative synthesis. The effectiveness of IASTM in the management of athletic and musculoskeletal conditions was found to be either better or equal in comparison to other control interventions. The meta-analysis results showed that the reduction in pain was statistically significant in the experimental group (IASTM) compared to the control group (MD -1.33, 95% CI [-1.59, -1.06], $p < 0.0001$). Their study concluded that IASTM is an effective tool in the management of athletic and musculoskeletal conditions. Further studies

- should concentrate on investigating the efficiency of IASTM on particular participants with various specific athletic and musculoskeletal conditions [7].
- Lambart et al., (2017)** conducted a systematic review to systematically examine evidence on the effectiveness of IASTM, compared to other interventions on patients with pain and disability resulting from musculoskeletal impairments. Numerous databases were searched using the terms Instrument Assisted Soft Tissue, Pain, Function, Graston, and soft tissue mobilization (STM). Inclusion criteria included: randomized clinical trials on patients with musculoskeletal impairments, STM had to be a treatment intervention, performed on human subjects, and had to capture a measure of pain or function. Articles were excluded if they were not published in English or if the subjects were of the pediatric or geriatric populations. Included articles were appraised using the Physiotherapy Evidence Database (PEDro) scale. Seven studies met the inclusion criteria. All seven articles scored a minimum 4/10 on the PEDro scale. The studies involved treatment of numerous anatomical locations and the majority of the studies demonstrated significant improvements in pain and/or range of motion when compared to control or other conservative treatment groups. Their study concluded that IASTM may have an impact on physiological changes by providing an increase in blood flow, reduction in tissue viscosity, myofascial release, interruption of pain receptors, and improvement of flexibility of underlying tissue. It is suggested that IASTM is an effective treatment intervention for reducing pain and improving function in less than a three-month period [9].
 - Tang et al., (2025)** conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis to evaluate the effectiveness of IASTM on pain and function in patients with musculoskeletal disorders. The researchers searched the PubMed, Embase, Web of Science, and Cochrane Library databases to identify randomized controlled trials comparing treatment groups receiving IASTM combined with other treatments to those receiving other treatments among participants with musculoskeletal disorders. The outcomes were pain intensity, pain pressure threshold and function. The Cochran Q and I² indices were used to estimate heterogeneity. The data were analyzed as the standardized mean difference (SMD). The Cochrane Risk of Bias tool was used to assess the risk of bias. The Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development, and Evaluation system was used to rate the quality of evidence. Trial sequential analysis and sensitivity analyses were also performed. Eleven trials (involving 427 participants) were included in the quantitative analysis. Six trials had a high risk of bias; three, unclear; and two, low. There was moderate-certainty evidence indicating that IASTM was effective in reducing patient-reported pain (n=11) (n=427, SMD=0.60, 95% CI: 0.41 to 0.80, p<0.01), and there was low-certainty evidence indicating that IASTM was effective in improving patient-reported function (n=8) (n=333, SMD=0.40, 95% CI: 0.03 to 0.77, p<0.05). Only one data point was extracted for the pain pressure threshold, and a meta-analysis was not performed. Trial sequential analysis revealed that the cumulative z score crossed the monitoring boundary for superiority for patient-reported pain in patients with nonspecific chronic neck pain and cervicogenic headache at the 4-week IASTM. Their study concluded that IASTM can reduce patient-reported pain (with moderate certainty) and improve patient-reported function (with low certainty) in patients with musculoskeletal disorders. Future clinical studies do not need to explore the short-term effects of IASTM on patient-reported pain in patients with nonspecific chronic neck pain and cervicogenic headache [10].

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Search Strategy:

A literature search was carried out using keywords “Instrument-Assisted Soft Tissue Mobilization (IASTM)”, “Graston Technique”, “ASTYM therapy”, “tendinopathy”, and “musculoskeletal rehabilitation”. Google Scholar, PubMed, Scopus and ScienceDirect databases were utilized for performing the searches. Studies published between **2015 and 2025** were considered for this review. Boolean operators “AND” and “OR” were used to refine and combine the search terms.

Inclusion Criteria:

Articles were considered if they were :

- Published in English
- Accessible as full articles
- Involved patients with tendinopathy or related musculoskeletal conditions
- Used IASTM techniques like Graston or ASTYM as a treatment method
- Assessed outcomes such as pain, strength, range of motion, or functional improvement

Exclusion Criteria:

Articles were excluded if :

- Work that wasn't published
- Proceedings of conferences
- Review based articles

Data Extraction:

439 studies were identified after the keyword search in various databases. The studies were selected carefully screening their texts based on the eligibility criteria. After eligibility screening 15 studies were selected. The included articles were then reviewed and analysed qualitatively to understand the effectiveness of IASTM in the management of tendinopathies. 4 studies were included in this literature review study.

Participant Characteristics:

The studies included participants suffering from different tendon-related conditions such as lateralelbow tendinopathy, Achilles

tendinopathy, and chronic plantar heel pain. In total, 206 participants were included across the selected studies, most of whom were adults experiencing pain and functional limitations due to tendon disorders.

Study Design:

The selected studies included randomized controlled trials, comparative studies, and pilot randomized trials. These studies were conducted in different countries including Turkey, Pakistan, and the United States.

Outcome Measures:

Different outcome measures were used to assess the effectiveness of IASTM. Intensity of pain was commonly measured using the Visual Analog Scale. Functional outcomes were studied using tools such as PRTEE (Patient-Rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation), VISA-A, and DASH. Other measures included a hand dynamometer, functional performance, first-step pain in plantar heel pain. These outcome measures helped evaluate improvements in pain, strength, and overall function.

RESULTS

This literature review included four studies. These studies evaluated the effectiveness of (IASTM) on conditions such as lateral elbow tendinopathy, Achilles tendinopathy, and chronic plantar heel pain. The selected studies included Different types of studies RCT, Pilot Studies etc. In total, 206 participants were involved across these studies. Overall, the findings showed that IASTM helped reduce pain, improve grip strength, and enhance functional performance in individuals with tendon-related conditions.

Some studies compared IASTM with other treatments such as eccentric exercise programs and extracorporeal shock wave therapy. Although all groups showed improvement, patients who received IASTM along with exercise therapy generally experienced faster pain relief and better functional outcomes. For example, individuals with lateral elbow tendinopathy showed significant improvement

in pain and grip strength, while patients with Achilles tendinopathy reported quicker symptom relief when techniques like the Graston method were used. Overall, the results suggest that IASTM can be a helpful addition to physiotherapy rehabilitation for managing tendinopathies [1,2,4,8]. Table 1 and 2 summarizes the characteristics of the included studies and PICO parameters of the included studies respectively.

Table 1: Characteristics of included studies

Sr. No.	Author, Year, Country	Sample & Research Design	Objective	Procedure	Outcome Variables	Result
1	Gercek H., Sonmez Unuvar B., et al, 2025, Turkey [1]	48 adults with lateral elbow pain; Randomized single-blind clinical trial	Compare IASTM + exercise vs ESWT + exercise vs exercise alone	3 groups treated; assessed baseline, post-treatment, 4-week follow-up	VAS pain, PRTEE, grip strength	All improved; IASTM came to be superior
2	Qureshi A.U., et al., 2024, Pakistan [2]	40 Achilles tendinopathy patients; Randomized comparative study	Compare Graston vs Alfredson protocol	Two groups treated for 8 weeks	Pain, function, VISA-A	Both improved; Graston effected faster
3	Jones E.R., Finley M.A., et al 2019, USA [4]	11 with chronic plantar heel pain; Pilot RCT	Test feasibility/effect of adding IASTM	Both got exercises; And also, IASTM	Pain, first-step pain, function	Both improved; IASTM effect sizes larger
4	Sevier T.L., Stegink-Jansen C., 2015, USA [8]	107 patients (113 elbows); Randomized controlled trial	Compare ASTYM vs eccentric exercise	Two groups; non-responders crossed over	DASH, pain, grip strength	ASTYM 78.3% improvement vs 40.9% eccentric exercise

Table 2: PICO parameters of the included studies

Author ; Year; Country	Population	Intervention	Comparison	Outcome Variables
Gercek H., Sonmez Unuvar B., et al, 2025, Turkey [1]	Lateral epicondylitis patients	Instrument Assisted Soft Tissue Mobilization	Exercise , Extra corporeal shock wave therapy	Pain, PRTEE, grip strength
Qureshi A.U., et al., 2024, Pakistan [2]	Achilles tendinopathy patients	Gratsonprotocol	Alfredson protocol	Pain, function, VISA-A
Jones E.R., Finley M.A., et al 2019, USA [4]	Plantar heel pain patients	Instrument Assisted Soft Tissue Manipulation	Exercises	Pain, first-step pain, function

Sevier T.L., Stegink-Jansen C., 2015, USA [8]	Lateral epicondylitis	Augmented Soft Tissue Mobilization	Eccentric exercises	DASH, pain, grip strength
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Abbreviations:

VAS: Visual Analog Scale; **PRTEE:** Patient-Rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation; **VISA-A:** Victorian Institute of Sport Assessment–Achilles Questionnaire; **DASH:** Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder and Hand Questionnaire; **ESWT:** Extracorporeal Shock Wave Therapy; **IASTM:** Instrument-Assisted Soft Tissue Mobilization; **ASTYM:** Augmented Soft Tissue Mobilization; **RCT:** Randomized Controlled Trial

Additional Analysis:

Pain decreased significantly in the included studies, followed by grip strength amongst the individuals suffering from various types of tendinopathies. However, other interventions like eccentric exercises and extra corporeal shock wave therapy were also aiding in the faster recovery. All the included studies supported the fact that IASTM was effective in providing relief from pain and increasing the muscular strength along with the adjunct interventions [1,2,4,8].

Gercek H., Sonmez Unuvar B., et al (2025) conducted a randomized single-blind clinical trial comparing the effects of instrument-assisted soft tissue mobilization (IASTM) and extracorporeal shock wave therapy (ESWT) in individuals with lateral elbow pain (LEP). The study included 48 adult participants randomly assigned to three groups: IASTM + home exercise, ESWT + home exercise, and control (home exercise only). Outcomes measured were pain via the Visual Analog Scale (VAS), grip strength using a hand dynamometer, and functionality through the Patient-Rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation (PRTEE) at baseline, post-treatment and at four-week follow-up. Results showed that all groups improved significantly ($P < .001$).

Qureshi A U., et al., (2024) conducted a comparative study of the Graston Technique versus the Alfredson eccentric protocol in patients with Achilles tendinopathy. The study

included 40 participants randomized between the two interventions and measured outcomes like pain, functional ability, and the VISA-A score over a period of eight weeks. Findings showed both groups improved, but the Graston group achieved quicker symptom relief, likely because of mechanical stimulation and enhanced local circulation afforded by the instrument-assisted method. The Alfredson group improved more gradually. The authors recommended that instrument-assisted soft tissue mobilization be considered alongside eccentric loading to optimize clinical outcomes in Achilles tendinopathy.

Jones E. R., Finley M. A, et al., 2019 carried out a pilot randomized trial to explore whether adding Grastontechnique IASTM to standard physiotherapy care is feasible and potentially effective for people with chronic plantar heel pain (CPHP). Eleven participants with heel pain for 6 weeks up to a year were divided into two groups, both groups got stretching, exercises, and a home program, but one group also received IASTM. They measured pain (including first-step pain in the morning) and function at the start, after treatment, and 90 days later. The study found that both groups improved, but the IASTM group showed medium-to-large effect sizes compared to control. Based on their data, the authors estimated that a future study would need at least 42 participants to reliably detect a difference. They concluded that using IASTM (Graston) for CPHP seems feasible and promising enough to merit a larger trial.

Sevier TL, Stegink-Jansen C, (2015) conducted a randomized controlled trial comparing ASTYM instrumentassisted soft tissue mobilization with an eccentric exercise program for chronic lateral elbow tendinopathy. The trial involved 107 participants with 113 affected elbows, divided into two treatment groups and followed for up to twelve months. Outcome measures included DASH scores, pain during activity, grip strength and functional performance. The

findings showed that the ASTYM group achieved a much higher symptom resolution rate, with 78.3% improvement compared to 40.9% in the eccentric exercise group. An important observation was that most patients who did not respond to eccentric loading showed significant improvement after being switched to ASTYM, with 95.7% achieving resolution. The authors suggested that instrument-assisted soft tissue mobilization may offer faster and more consistent results, especially for individuals who do not respond adequately to exercise alone.

DISCUSSION

This literature review included only four studies due to limited access to the databases. There were few studies which included tendinopathy affected patients undergone IASTM treatment. The findings show that IASTM can be a useful part of treating tendinopathies. In many studies, patients who received IASTM had less pain, better grip strength, and improved overall function. These improvements are important because tendon problems often make daily activities difficult and affect quality of life. Since similar results were seen across different studies, it suggests that IASTM may help the healing process and bring the affected area back to normal function.

Another key point is how IASTM is actually used in practice. It is usually not used alone but combined with other treatments like strengthening exercises (especially eccentric), stretching, and functional training. This combination seems to work better than exercise alone. It indicates that IASTM might prepare the soft tissues and help them respond better to exercise and loading.

Common techniques like Graston Technique and ASTYM therapy are often used. These methods work by applying controlled pressure to the soft tissues, which may help break down scar tissue or adhesions, improve blood flow, and stimulate healing. Because of this, patients often feel pain relief faster and notice better movement, especially in the early stages of treatment.

Limitations of the study:

This literature review has a few limitations. Small sample size, heterogeneity in tools, treatment frequency, tendon sites, exercise protocols and follow-up [1-4]. Most studies only looked at short-term results. There is not enough information about long-term benefits or whether the condition comes back after treatment. The exploration regarding whether IASTM works more effectively as a standalone treatment or when combined with exercise-based rehabilitation programs was not possible due to limited access to the databases and lack of relevant studies. So, even though the current results are promising and support using IASTM along with other rehab methods, more high-quality research with larger groups and proper standard protocols is needed. This will help give clearer guidance to clinicians treating tendinopathies. First, only a small number of studies were included because access to databases was limited. Second, a meta-analysis was not done, so the results are based on a general review rather than a detailed statistical analysis.

Future scope of the study:

Future research should aim to include more high-quality RCTs and perform a proper meta-analysis. This will help give a clearer picture of how effective (IASTM) really is in treating tendinopathies and related issues like pain, limited movement, and reduced function.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that IASTM may be a useful adjunct to exercise-based rehabilitation for selected tendinopathy conditions; however, larger high-quality randomized controlled trials with standardized protocols and long-term follow-up are required.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest was declared by the authors.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Sincere thanks to the Department of Physiotherapy, Sharda School of Allied Health

Sciences, Sharda University, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh.

Ethical Declaration:

This study is in accordance with the institutional ethical guidelines.

Funding:

This study receives no grant via any agency.

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